

FACTORS FOR PERFECTING THE ACTIVITIES OF THE MODERN LEADER

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Abstract. This article discusses perfecting modern leaders' innovation, creative approach, and effective collaboration with employees. It also considers the openness of a leader's activities, increasing work efficiency, and inspiring the diligence and enthusiasm of employees when managing and motivating a team.

Keywords: Persuasion, consent, engagement, encouragement, leadership, unification, collaboration, efficiency, sincerity, openness, consistency, systematicity.

Today, leadership requires not only the effective management of organizations but also innovation, a creative approach, and effective collaboration with employees. As a rule, modern leaders must be able to think systematically, use modern information technologies in decision-making, and play a leading role in guiding the team towards progressive goals. For this reason, the issue of perfecting a leader's activities is of critical importance. In the context of the complex processes in today's global economy, the fiercely competitive environment in domestic and foreign markets, and the new socio-economic reforms being implemented in the country, it is vital to identify, study, analyze, and research the factors that ensure the success of modern organizations, as well as to introduce them into management processes, constantly improve them, and increase their effectiveness. One of these factors is the intellectual potential, knowledge, qualifications, and work attitude of the leader-managers who ensure the organization's success.

As the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh.M. Mirziyoyev emphasized, "Modern management personnel and managers should not only possess high professional skills, but also be educated in every respect, knowledgeable in their fields, proactive, dedicated to their assigned tasks, and approach problem-solving creatively. Most importantly, they must be true patriots of our Motherland"[1]. "To implement our large-scale plans, we will need to carry out a number of measures to improve the entire system of working with personnel." This is because modern personnel set society in motion, awaken the creative powers, initiative, and aspirations of the people, and revitalize their socio-economic and spiritual life. When a leader is exemplary and well-rounded in every respect, able to convince

It is not without reason that the Japanese sages said: "A good leader grows rice, a bad one grows wormwood, a wise one cultivates the land, a far-sighted one trains personnel." Before studying the practical aspects of leadership, it is advisable to learn the basic concepts, methods, and tools related to it. All this contributes to a correct understanding of the essence of leadership activity and its effective organization and successful implementation. What is management, and who is the leader (manager)? - scholars and specialists give various definitions. Some say that management is a science that trains managerial personnel for management activities, while others say that management is the activation of people in management activities. In the fundamental Oxford Dictionary of the English Language,

management is interpreted as "the art of power and management, the ways in which people interact." [3].

The main factors for improving the activities of a modern manager are that a modern manager should pay attention to continuous education and professional development, that is, attend training and courses on management and leadership, learn new technologies and methodologies, and develop analytical and creative thinking in the work process. Today, IT tools make the work of a modern manager much more effective, namely: mastering online analysis and reporting systems, video conferencing and virtual team management, and automated decision-making systems. One of the main tasks of a leader in managing and motivating a team is to increase the efficiency and motivation of employees. This can be achieved by correctly assessing the abilities of each employee, clearly defining goals and objectives, and implementing a system of moral and material incentives. A modern leader must not only solve everyday tasks, but also effectively manage long-term plans and strategies. For this, it is necessary to use methods of analysis and forecasting.

Leadership is the manager's managerial activity. Motivation is the process of material and moral encouragement of an individual employee or group of employees in accordance with their effective work towards the overall goals of the organization. According to sociologist Robert Birsted, "power stands behind every organization and maintains its structure. Without authority, there is neither organization nor order"[5].

Leadership is the ability to influence people and groups to work towards achieving goals. Effective management and effective leadership are not the same thing. Therefore, the question of what is necessary to be a leader and to be an effective leader is one of the important issues in the science of management. According to the behavioral approach to understanding leadership, leadership is determined not by the leader's personal qualities, but by their behavior and conduct towards subordinates. The main contribution of this approach to management science is the classification of leadership styles. At the same time, the main disadvantage of this approach is the belief that there is only one optimal leadership style. Modern leadership theory focuses more on a situational approach. According to this, the leader's manifestation of certain personal qualities, behavior, and conduct depends on the specific situation. This approach complements and improves both of the above approaches. In leadership activities, it is important to know and be able to rationally use management methods and styles. Thus, leadership methods and techniques are understood as a set of guidelines for effectively influencing the management object, taking into account the specific interests of an individual employee, group, or team. Based on the invaluable role of modern leaders in solving problems hindering today's development, utilizing existing reserves and opportunities, successfully solving and implementing pressing issues and priority tasks, it is necessary to systematically improve their activities. [5]

In conclusion, it should be noted that today, along with the consistent and systematic reforms being carried out in the country to improve the management system, as in all spheres, we believe that the analysis, practical proposals, and recommendations made in this study will show their positive results in improving the implementation of leadership activities in organizations, introducing new mechanisms, and eliminating and solving issues, complexities, and shortcomings awaiting solutions in the field of management. Improving modern leadership is a continuous process, and education, IT technologies, effective teamwork, innovation, and

strategic thinking are the key to the success of a modern leader. When these factors are effectively applied, the organization and team achieve their goals quickly and effectively.

References:

1. Mirziyoyev Sh.M. We will resolutely continue our path of national development and raise it to a new level. - T.: "Uzbekistan" NMIU, 2019.
2. Mirziyoyev Sh.M. From National Revival to National Ascent.-T.: "Uzbekistan" NMIU, 2020.
3. To'xtaboyev A.T. Manager Qualities / Practical Guide. -T.: MATRIX PRINT LLC, 2008. 172 p. Michael Mescon, Michael Albert, Franklin Hedouri. Fundamentals of Management. Publishing House: "ID "Williams,"" - 2008.
5. Tukhtaboev A.T. Organizational actions. Textbook.-T.: "University," 2021. 260 pages.

